

Adrenocortical_cells time clusters

Amacrine_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 152

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 169

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 226

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 203

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 231

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 213

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 188

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 200

Antigen_presenting_cells time clusters

Bipolar_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 186

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 187

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 154

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 201

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 148

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 188

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 159

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 140

Bronchiolar_and_alveolar_epithelial_cells time clusters

Cardiomyocytes time clusters

Chromaffin_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 346

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 143

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 239

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 640

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 19

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 414

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 72

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 718

Corneal_and_conjunctival_epithelial_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 361

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 472

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 446

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 366

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 468

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 359

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 358

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 383

CSH1_CSH2_positive_cells time clusters

Ductal_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 3

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 58

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 261

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1390

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1702

Endocardial_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 43

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 39

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 221

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 217

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 239

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 672

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 59

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 514

ENS_glia time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 326

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 312

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 397

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 195

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 328

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 273

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 287

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 247

ENS_neurons time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 357

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 388

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 435

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 424

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 153

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 317

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 404

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 480

Epicardial_fat_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 9

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 807

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 19

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 586

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 189

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 34

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 334

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 699

Erythroblasts time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 63

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 39

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 614

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 67

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 64

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 310

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 815

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 46

Excitatory_neurons time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 444

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 441

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 422

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 347

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 365

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 414

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 471

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 407

Extravillous_trophoblasts time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 457

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 193

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 360

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 28

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 143

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 439

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 504

Ganglion_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 282

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 325

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 332

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 355

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 263

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 413

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 349

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 383

Goblet_cells time clusters

Granule_neurons time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 327

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 463

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 338

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 355

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 355

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 271

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 354

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 396

Hematopoietic_stem_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 638

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 313

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 168

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 455

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 410

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 506

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 113

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 25

Hepatoblasts time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 243

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 275

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 330

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 200

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 205

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 213

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 188

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 205

Horizontal_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 185

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 223

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 187

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 205

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 203

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 249

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 217

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 193

Inhibitory_interneurons time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 375

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 400

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 366

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 352

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 382

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 329

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 327

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 274

Inhibitory_neurons time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 365

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 516

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 394

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 534

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 564

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 500

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 547

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 646

Intestinal_epithelial_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 48

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 283

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 276

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1631

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 131

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 49

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1808

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 257

Lens_fibre_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 297

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 316

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 355

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 319

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 304

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 313

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 250

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 299

Mesangial_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 511

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 750

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 18

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 87

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1090

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 68

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 77

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 621

Metanephric_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 2638

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 2591

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 6

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 2

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 1

MUC13_DMBT1_positive_cells time clusters

Myeloid_cells time clusters

Oligodendrocytes time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 377

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 395

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 384

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 322

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 532

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 487

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 319

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 172

PAEP_MECOM_positive_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 240

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 324

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 260

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 305

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 185

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 272

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 239

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 203

Parietal_and_chief_cells time clusters

PDE11A_FAM19A2_positive_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 217

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 197

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 219

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 265

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 243

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 226

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 222

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 238

PDE1C_ACSM3_positive_cells time clusters

Photoreceptor_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 201

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 222

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 211

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 197

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 249

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 189

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 214

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 211

Purkinje_neurons time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 641

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 568

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 596

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 660

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 623

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 608

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 582

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 671

Retinal_pigment_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 212

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 222

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 220

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 234

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 188

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 213

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 238

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 188

Retinal_progenitors_and_Muller_glia time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 222

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 200

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 225

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 227

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 175

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 214

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 197

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 221

SATB2_LRRC7_positive_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 124

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 206

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 339

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 198

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 498

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 254

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 249

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 228

Satellite_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 133

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 216

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 347

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 409

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 36

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 427

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 26

SKOR2_NPSR1_positive_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 165

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 559

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 759

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 515

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 732

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 478

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 742

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 693

SLC24A4_PEX5L_positive_cells time clusters

SLC26A4_PAEP_positive_cells time clusters

Smooth_muscle_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 296

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 31

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 21

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 864

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 3

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 40

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 45

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 615

Stellate_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 276

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 212

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 82

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 241

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 156

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 213

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 311

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 289

Syncytiotrophoblasts_and_villous_cytotrophoblasts time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 249

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 319

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 239

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 464

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 12

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 503

Thymocytes time clusters

Trophoblast_giant_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 257

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 228

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 193

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 222

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 182

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 169

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 154

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 155

Unipolar_brush_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 250

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 249

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 217

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 235

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 265

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 287

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 211

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 270

Ureteric_bud_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1067

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 2

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1358

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 663

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 2251

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 5

Vascular_endothelial_cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 996

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 345

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 469

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 144

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 743

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 444

